

Implementation of enhanced biological phosphorus recovery for phosphorus mining from eutrophic marine sediments: The optimization of parameters and exploration of microbial responses

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate the feasibility of enriching polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (PAOs) within marine sediment for achieving phosphorus (P) recovery, two sediment-inoculated sequencing batch reactors (SBRs), fed with propionic acid (R1) and glucose (R2), were operated for 119 days. For comparison, two sewage sludge-inoculated reactors (R3 and R4) were also set up. The sediments/sludge fed with 200 mg/L chemical oxygen demand (COD) equivalent propionic acid exhibited satisfactory P release/uptake performance after 56 days of culture. The maximum P release and uptake rates for R1 were 3 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹ and 2.5 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹, respectively, while for R3 they were 2.6 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹ and 5.8 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹, respectively. Meanwhile, the PAO family (*Rhodocyclaceae*) in R1 increased from almost 0 % initially to 16.0 % after 42 days. However, the glucose-fed SBRs did not exhibit enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) performance throughout the operation. As the COD feeding concentration increased to 400 mg/L, the reactors showed EBPR deterioration. Total P in R1 and R3 significantly decreased from 423.7 mg and from 368.0 mg to 94.9 mg, respectively. Key intracellular polymer responses indicated that introduction of excessively high COD significantly reduced poly-P content and the anaerobic synthesis of polyhydroxyalkanoate. Microbial analysis suggested that the breakdown of EBPR performance could be attributed to glycogen-accumulating organisms outcompeting PAOs under high carbon feeding conditions. Additionally, PHREEQC simulations confirmed that P-rich supernatant from the anaerobic phase could theoretically be recovered as struvite, with a recovery efficiency of up to 94 %.

1. Introduction

Phosphate rock as one of the essential resources for industry, is primarily sourced from a limited number of countries/regions (i.e., Morocco, China, Egypt) [1]. Due to its critical role in the production of phosphorus (P) fertilizers, as well as its restricted availability and heavy reliance on imports, the European Union (EU) designated it as a Critical Raw Material in 2014 [2]. However, excessive P input has led to eutrophication issues, particularly evident in regions of the Baltic Sea. The observation data indicated that 97 % of marine areas have degraded due to eutrophication, with the total P reservoir in the Baltic Sea

continuing to increase [3]. According to the research of Kotta et al. [3], current efforts to manage eutrophication primarily focus on reducing external nutrient inputs of the Baltic Sea, overlooking the internal release of legacy P from marine sediments.

Therefore, internal measures to capture P directly from the marine system should be prioritized and employed, in this scenario, P present in eutrophic marine could probably be a promising source for recovery, offering a dual benefit by simultaneously addressing the burden of excess nutrient loading. In recent years, technologies focused on P recovery, primarily from waste streams, have made significant strides. Enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR) process has been well

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established based on aerobic or denitrifying polyphosphate accumulating organisms (PAOs) [4], for example, the study of Oehmen et al. demonstrated that in EBPR systems, a higher pH (~8) gives an advantage to PAOs over glycogen-accumulating organisms (GAOs), resulting in improved P removal efficiency [5]. Guisasola et al. successfully operated a long-term EBPR system for over one year with an influent chemical oxygen demand of 300 mg/L (COD/P of 7.5), demonstrating excellent performance and stability. Additionally, they achieved a recovery of up to 60 % of the P through anaerobic supernatant extraction [6].

The significant role of PAOs in P removal/recovery has been confirmed by the aforementioned cases. However, the authors have not found any research on enriching PAOs from eutrophic marine sediment under alternating anaerobic and aerobic conditions for improving P recovery. Considering the alternating anaerobic–aerobic environment in the seabed and our previous 16S sequencing results from the batch experiments, which confirmed the presence of PAOs in the Baltic Sea marine sediment despite their low abundance (only 1–2 % at the family level) [7]. Our earlier paper proposed in the future outlook section that, due to the low abundance of functional PAOs, achieving the desired anaerobic carbon (C) absorption and subsequent P release for recovery purposes is challenging [7]. Therefore, we hypothesized that by providing a certain proportion of C and P sources, along with alternating aerobic-anaerobic conditions, PAOs in sediment can be enriched, thus improving sediment suitability for P recovery. Therefore, the feasibility of applying relevant processes to mine P from marine sediments need to be investigated.

The type and concentration of C feeding sources play a crucial role in the enrichment of PAO and the competition between PAO and GAO within EBPR systems. For example, Lopez-Vazquez et al. [8] assessed the metabolic models under different C sources (acetate and propionate) and their ratios to evaluate the competition between PAO and GAO. The results confirmed significant impacts of different C sources on the competition, as well as the enrichment of PAO species. When acetate was the sole C source, *Accumulibacter* (one of typical PAOs) dominated the system at 10 °C, comprising more than 60 % of the bacterial population. However, at 30 °C and with an influent acetate to propionate ratio of 75:25 %, *Accumulibacter* lost dominance at pH 6. Similarly, in another PAO and GAO competition study with an EBPR system, Oehmen et al. [9] found out that propionate might be a more effective C source than acetate for running EBPR, offering PAOs a competitive advantage over GAOs. Systems supplied with acetate often exhibited unstable P removal due to GAO outcompeting for acetate uptake, whereas those fed with propionate showed higher and more stable P removal levels and lower effluent P concentrations.

Besides the type of the feeding C sources, C dosage concentration and the C/P ratio are also crucial for the enrichment of PAOs during the acclimation phase. The research by Majed and Gu [10] demonstrated that changes in the influent COD/P ratio affected the relative abundance of PAOs and GAOs, as well as EBPR performance and system stability. An increase in influent C/P ratio (from 20 to 50) resulted in a decrease in the overall abundance of total PAOs and *Accumulibacter*-like PAOs, while total GAOs and candidate GAOs *Competibacter* increased in the microbial community. However, contrasting results were reported by Mielczarek et al. [11], who conducted a comprehensive three-year survey on the population dynamics of PAO and GAO in 28 nutrient removal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in Denmark. The results revealed that two PAO genera, *Accumulibacter* and *Tetrasphaera*, were abundant in all EBPR WWTPs. The C/P ratio (varying from 40 to 115) correlated with *Accumulibacter* in nearly all plants, and *Tetrasphaera* types were positively correlated with high organic loading. Therefore, it is essential to determine the appropriate C/P ratio and feeding C source type, as well as concentrations, based on specific EBPR systems. These parameters require specific experimentation and exploration.

Our previous batch research indicated that glucose, as an easily assimilated C source, led to significant anaerobic consumption, with

more than 5 g/L of glucose consumed by sediments within 12 days; and simultaneously promoted P release from the sediment [12]. In addition to glucose, propionic acid, as one of the VFAs (volatile fatty acids), also demonstrated a beneficial influence on anaerobic P release. Two-way ANOVA analysis revealed that both glucose and propionic acid addition significantly promoted P release from the Baltic Sea sediment over a 15-day anaerobic batch period compared to acetic acid and butyric acid ($p < 0.05$). However, at a concentration of 1 g/L, there was no significant difference between the glucose- and propionic acid-fed systems regarding P release ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, in our experiment, the two C sources, glucose and propionic acid, were selected for feeding inoculated SBRs with the Baltic Sea sediments. Additionally, sewage sludge-inoculated SBRs were also set up as comparative groups. The objectives of this study were: (1) to investigate the feasibility of PAO enrichment within marine sediment (specific to eutrophic Baltic Sea sediment) using EBPR technology; (2) to optimize the operational parameters for SBRs, such as optimal C sources and C/P ratios for enhancing PAO abundance; (3) to elucidate the EBPR performance under different operational conditions and the corresponding microbial mechanisms in sediment and sludge; and (4) to conduct preliminary software simulations exploring the theoretical feasibility of P recovery via precipitation, providing valuable insights for subsequent efforts in P recovery from sediments.

2. Method and material

2.1. SBR operation

Four SBRs with 1.5 L working volume were operated with 8 h cycles, each cycle consisted of 2 h of anaerobic phase (initial 10 min for feeding), 4 h of aerobic phase, and 2 h of settling/decant phase. Initially, the reactors were seeded with marine sediment from the eutrophic Baltic Sea region (characterization details seen in Zhu et al. [7]) and aerobic sludge from local KÄPPAL WWTP in Sweden, respectively. The characterization of sludge can be found in Table S1. Subsequently, both sediment- and sludge-inoculated reactors were operated using different C sources, propionic acid and glucose. A schematic diagram illustrating the operation of the four SBRs is presented in Fig. 1. Specifically, the SBR inoculated with sediment and fed with propionic acid is designated as reactor 1 (R1), the SBR inoculated with sediment and fed with glucose is designated as reactor 2 (R2), the SBR inoculated with sludge and fed with propionic acid is designated as reactor 3 (R3), and the SBR inoculated with sludge and fed with glucose is designated as reactor 4 (R4).

Considering the low biological reactivity of the sediment, the initial volatile suspended solids (VSS) for the reactors inoculated with marine sediment and sludge were set at 5 g/L and 2 g/L, respectively. The reactors were operated with a hydraulic retention time of 24 h and a $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ loading rate of 45 mg P per day. During each cycle, in the feeding phase, 0.5 L of a fresh solution containing gradually increasing C concentrations (based on COD value) was fed. In the acclimation phase, the concentration of the C source was progressively increased, following a sequence of 50 mg/L, 100 mg/L, 200 mg/L, and 400 mg/L of COD. To be more specific, during acclimation period I, a COD/P ratio of 5 (50 mg/L COD) was maintained for 7 weeks (Day 0 to Day 41); in acclimation period II, the ratio increased from 5 to 10 (100 mg COD/L), and maintained for two weeks (Day 42 to Day 55). After observing significant P release/uptake, the C/P ratio was changed to 20 (200 mg COD/L) (Day 56 to Day 77), and later increased to 40 (400 mg/L COD). However, when the COD concentration was increased to 400 mg/L, a rapid decrease in the anaerobic P release of propionic-fed SBRs was observed. Therefore, three weeks later, the COD feeding concentration was adjusted back to 200 mg/L, and the reactors were operated for an additional three weeks to observe the response of sediment/sludge. All SBRs were operated for a total of 119 days.

A synthetic medium following the protocol outlined in Guisasola et al. [6], which was consistently supplied, consisting of (mg/L): 30.0 of

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of operated reactors.

NaHCO₃, 100 of NH₄Cl, 57 of MgSO₄, 248 of MgCl₂·6H₂O, 42.0 of CaCl₂·2H₂O, and 5.0 of Allylthiourea (used to inhibit nitrification). Additionally, a micronutrient solution was added at a volume of 30 mL per liter, with the following composition (g/L): 1.50 of FeCl₃·6H₂O, 0.15 of H₃BO₃, 0.03 of CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.18 of KI, 0.12 of MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.06 of Na₂MoO₄·4H₂O, 0.12 of ZnSO₄·7H₂O, 0.15 of CoCl₂·6H₂O, and 10 of EDTA. Sodium propionate and glucose were used as C sources at the concentrations specified in the above text, and 5 g/L of a P stock solution containing 13.6 g/L of KH₂PO₄ and 10.3 K₂HPO₄. The C feeding solution along with the synthetic medium, trace elements, and P were prepared and delivered to the reactor using a pump with a flow rate of 50 mL/min. The temperature was kept at room temperature (around 25°C), and feeding solution pH 7.5 ± 0.1. During anaerobic phase, a constant flow of nitrogen gas was spared into the SBRs to ensure the anaerobic condition, during aerobic phase, air was bubbled at an approximate flow rate of 0.3 L/min. The stirring rate was kept at 300 rpm during the anaerobic and aerobic phases.

2.2. Chemical and biochemical analyses

The reactors' performance was assessed through biological and chemical analyses. The first cycle on sampling days was dedicated to measuring the PO₄-P concentration and C consumption in the supernatant and sediment/sludge at the end of different SBR operation stages. During the acclimation stage, sampling was conducted three times per week, which was later reduced to once per week, with total suspended solids (TSS) and VSS determined weekly. Starting from Day 70, we observed notable effective P release/uptake from propionic acid-fed EBPRs. Consequently, weekly sampling and analysis of intracellular

polymers (poly-P, polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA), and glycogen) were initiated at the end of each SBR operational stage from Day 70. Additionally, to conduct P mass balance within the SBRs, the total P content in the sediment/sludge was measured on Day 70, 84, and 98.

The total P and COD in the supernatant were measured with DR 3900 Hach Lange spectrophotometer and cuvette tests (LCK 350, LCK 314, LCK 514 Hach Lange, Germany). The concentration of PO₄-P was determined using the Murphy-Riley biochemical method [13]. The propionic acid analysis was conducted using gas chromatography (GC) (Agilent Intuvo 9000), equipped with CP-Sil 5 CB column (25 m × 0.32 mm × 5 μm, Agilent) and a flame ionization detector as described by Khatami et al. [14]. Glucose concentration was assessed following Amplex® Red Glucose/Glucose Oxidase Assay Kit (Invitrogen™) protocol and measured using a Qubit 4 Fluorometer (ThermoFisher). TSS and VSS in mixed liquor were analyzed according to Standard Methods [15]. The total P content in sludge/sediment was initially using Standards, Measurements and Testing (SMT) extraction protocol [16] and subsequently analyzed via the vanadomolybdophosphoric acid colorimetric method following Standard Methods [15].

The poly-P content was determined using the protocol outlined by Aravind et al. [17], where the difference between hydrolyzed and unhydrolyzed samples indicates poly-P content. The PHA and glycogen in the biomass were measured following protocols described in the research of Majed and Gu [10] and Perez-Zabaleta et al. [18], respectively. For PHA extraction, lyophilised samples (10–20 mg) were treated with 2 mL of chloroform and 2 mL of methanol supplemented with 3% (v/v) H₂SO₄ and internal standard (100 mg benzoic acid), then incubated for 2 h at 100 °C in a thermo-heater block. After cooling, 1 mL of deionized water was added, followed by vigorous vortexing and phase

separation. The organic phase was transferred into GC glass vials, and 2 μL of the digested samples were injected into GC (Agilent Intuvo 9000), following the procedure outlined by Perez-Zabaleta et al. [18]. Standard PHAs including Methyl (R)-3-hydroxybutyrate (PHB), Methyl (R)-3-hydroxyvalerate (PHV) and 2-hydroxycaproic acid as standard for polyhydroxy-2-methylvalerate (PH2MV) were digested to build the standards. For glycogen content measurement, 10–20 mg of lyophilized pellets were treated with 2 mL of a dilute solution of 0.5 M HCl, followed by incubation in a heating block at 100 °C for 2 h. After cooling, the supernatant was extracted, filtered (0.22 μm), and the glycogen concentration was determined based on the glucose concentration and reported as mg glucose per mg of dry solids.

2.3. DNA extraction and Illumina high-throughput sequencing

Genomic DNA from microbial samples was extracted using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN, Germany), following the manufacturer's manual protocol. Library preparation was performed according to the Illumina 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). The V3-V4 hypervariable region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified via PCR in a final volume of 25 μL with 25 ng microbial DNA, 2X KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix (Roche, Basel, Switzerland), and 200 nmol/L of 341F and 785R primers with added Illumina adapter overhang sequences [19]. Amplification thermocycle consisted of 3 min at 95 °C, 25 cycles of 30 s at 95 °C, 30 s at 55 °C and 30 s at 72 °C, and a final 5-min step at 72 °C [20]. Purification of PCR products was performed with Agencourt AMPure XP magnetic beads (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) and indexed libraries were prepared by limited-cycle PCR with Nextera technology (Illumina). Libraries were cleaned-up as described above and then quantified using the Qubit 3.0 fluorimeter (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA), normalized to 4 nM and pooled. The sample pool was denatured with 0.2 N NaOH and diluted to a final concentration of 4.5 pM with a 20 % PhiX control. An Illumina MiSeq platform was used for sequencing using a 2 \times 250 bp paired-end protocol, according to the manufacturer's instructions (Illumina).

2.4. Statistical analysis

Microbial diversity analyses were conducted using R and SPSS software. Alpha diversity was assessed by plotting the Shannon entropy. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate the significance of differences in microbial diversity ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, differences in the relative abundance of phyla across different operational days were assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Performance of bioreactors by increasing the feeding carbon concentrations

The concentration of two feeding C sources was incrementally increased, ranging from 50 mg/L to 400 mg/L COD, based on C consumption and anaerobic P release performance. Biomass concentrations were monitored as mixed liquor suspended solids (MLSS) and mixed liquor volatile suspended solids (MLVSS) to understand the microbial growth and adaptation ability of different inocula during the different stages. As shown in Fig. S1(a), despite a decrease in MLSS concentration, a gradual increase in MLVSS was observed in all reactors during the operation. This was particularly evident in the sludge-seeded SBRs (Fig. S1(b)). For example, the MLVSS concentrations of R3 and R4 increased from 1412.5 mg/L and 1903.0 mg/L on Day 7 to 4826.5 mg/L and 6706.5 mg/L on Day 98, respectively. Notably, Fig. S1(b) also shows that, except for R1, the MLVSS in the other reactors decreased after Day 98. These changes can be attributed to microbial growth and adaptation under different C feeding periods. On the other hand, the VSS/TSS ratio

in sludge-inoculated reactors started around 0.45, gradually increased, and stabilized at around 0.8 after Day 49. At the same time, the VSS/TSS ratio in sediment-inoculated reactors started at lower values and increased gradually throughout the operation, rising from an initial 0.12 and 0.17 to a final 0.39 and 0.34 for R1 and R2, respectively. Additionally, during Day 42–56, the sediment-seeded reactors R1 and R2 had sludge retention time (SRT) of around 80 days, while the sludge-seeded reactors R3 and R4 maintained SRT around 70 days. However, starting from Day 70, as the sampling frequency was reduced from three times to once a week, the SRT increased for all reactors. The sediment-seeded reactors showed an increase to approximately 110 days, while the sludge-seeded reactors increased to about 85 days.

The results of $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ concentration profiles and COD consumption during different operation periods of the SBRs are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. S2, respectively. When the feeding COD concentration was only 50 mg/L, no significant anaerobic P release and aerobic P uptake were observed in all SBRs. However, when the feeding COD concentration increased to 100 mg/L, starting from Day 56, the SBRs fed with propionic acid in both the sediment- and sludge-inoculated reactors (R1 and R3) exhibited favorable P release/uptake performance. Conversely, no fluctuations in P concentration were observed in the two glucose-fed SBRs. More specific, as shown in the Fig. 2(a), the sediment-inoculated SBR fed with propionic acid (R1) exhibited satisfactory P release/uptake ability after 56 days of operation, with maximum P release and uptake rates of 3 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 2.5 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. While the corresponding rate of sludge-inoculated SBR (R3) were 2.6 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 5.8 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 2(c)). Compared to previous researches, the P uptake/release efficiency obtained in our study achieved a satisfactory level. In Guisasola et al.'s study, when the influent COD and P concentrations were 300 mg/L and 20 mg/L, respectively, the maximum P release efficiency was around 1 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. When the influent P concentration was increased to 40 mg/L, the efficiency also increased to 2.7 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [6]. Similar values were found in Wu et al.'s EBPR findings. When the influent C/P ratio decreased from 7 to 5 (from day 91 to day 224), the P uptake rate gradually increased from 0.7 to 3.75 mg P/g VSS $\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [4].

In our experiment, when the COD concentration was increased to 400 mg/L, the first 8-h data indicated that more anaerobic P release occurred in R1 and R3. However, as the operation continued, Fig. 2(a) and 2(c) illustrate that R1 and R3 notably lost their ability to release P anaerobically after one week. Therefore, starting from Day 105, the COD feeding concentration was reduced back to 200 mg/L. Despite this adjustment, all reactors exhibited poor EBPR performances.

For glucose-fed SBRs (R2 and R4, as seen in Fig. 2(b) and 2(d)), the capability of the sediment/sludge for P uptake and release did not enhance. This might be attributed to the different C source feeding causing variations in microbial selection between PAO and GAO. Similar results were observed in a study by Xie et al. [21], where feeding 100 % glucose led to a noticeable deterioration in EBPR performance. The authors analyzed and concluded that the failure of the reactor operation might be due to the competitive advantages of GAOs over PAOs. Another reason for the decline in EBPR performance could be that using glucose as the primary C source results in no fermentative bacteria in the reactor. Without these bacteria converting glucose into VFAs, PAOs cannot uptake glucose [22]. Details on microbial responses in our SBRs will be further discussed in the corresponding chapters.

When the COD feeding concentration was no higher than 200 mg/L, as shown in Fig. S2, all SBRs exhibited a rapid ability to consume C sources during the anaerobic phase (>70 % COD removal). In fact, in addition to monitoring COD consumption at different operation stages, we also tried to measure the concentrations of specific C sources (propionic acid and glucose) as seen in the Fig. S4. However, due to the rapid decomposition of the C sources, it was difficult to detect their concentrations as propionic acid and glucose after the 10 min feeding phase. Especially for the concentration of glucose, glucose was not detected in

Fig. 2. Historical $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ concentration profiles in (a) R1; (b) R2; (c) R3; (d) R4.

the bulk solution of SBR because it disappeared almost immediately upon feeding. Notably, when the COD feeding concentration increased to 400 mg/L, the propionic acid-fed reactors showed significant deterioration (Fig. 2). This was specifically evident in the dramatically reduced anaerobic P release and aerobic P uptake abilities in R1 and R3, where the anaerobic P release capacity nearly disappeared. Additionally, a noticeable change in color of the SBRs was observed during the reactor operation, as shown in Fig. S3. Another significant indicator was the markedly reduced COD consumption capacity during the anaerobic phase. After Day 91, the COD removal rate during the anaerobic phase for 400 mg/L COD was less than 30 %.

The C source is crucial for operating EBPR. Previous studies have shown that insufficient C addition can hinder EBPR performance. Therefore, researchers often enhance EBPR stability by increasing C concentrations [23,24]. However, our results also confirmed that excessively high C dosages can cause EBPR deterioration and significantly weaken anaerobic C uptake efficiency. Research by Ekholm [25] indicated that an extended anaerobic feeding phase favors the competition of PAOs and GAOs against aerobic heterotrophs, restricting the growth of aerobic heterotrophs by limiting the organic substrate available during the subsequent aerobic phase. Therefore, to some extent, anaerobic C consumption ability might serve as an indicator for deciding whether to increase carbon loading for the enhancement of PAO enrichment and anaerobic P release.

3.2. Phosphorus balance within SBRs

To further investigate the transformation of P in different stages of the SBRs under two C sources and various feeding concentrations, the analysis was conducted on analyzing the total P in the sediment/sludge

and supernatant. As depicted in Fig. 3, the majority of P was detected in the sediment/sludge rather than in the supernatant. Similar to the variations of $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ observed during operation, the total P in sediment and sludge-seeded SBRs fed with glucose remained at a stable, but relatively low level. Approximately 210 mg of P was present in glucose-fed sediment-inoculated SBR (Fig. 3(b)), while around 140 mg was found in sludge-inoculated SBR (Fig. 3(d)), significantly lower than the corresponding values of 424 and 368 mg observed in propionic acid-fed SBRs at their peak. This suggests that the reactors fed with glucose lacked the capacity for P uptake and accumulation.

On Day 70, when the feeding COD concentration was 200 mg/L, the total P content in R1 and R3 was 413.9 and 320.0 mg, respectively. During the anaerobic phase, P in the sediment/sludge was released into the supernatant, and during the aerobic phase, P was uptaken back into the sediment/sludge, demonstrating good P release and uptake performance. However, as the COD dosing concentration increased, although there was a slight initial rise in the P amount during the first cycle of feeding at 400 mg/L COD, reaching 423.7 and 368.0 mg of total P for R1 and R3, respectively, after two weeks of continuous operation of reactors at 400 mg/L COD, these values notably declined. The corresponding values significantly decreased, especially in the sludge-seeded SBR, dropping to as low as 95.0 mg, even lower than in the glucose-fed SBR. This may be related to the loss of microbial activity associated with poly-P metabolism under high C feeding conditions. When the system failed to effectively perform anaerobic P release and aerobic P uptake, P in the SBR was not enriched but instead got lost, further supporting the discussion on the deterioration of the EBPR system under 400 mg/L COD, as mentioned in the previous section.

Fig. 3. Phosphorus balance in the sediment/sludge and supernatant on Day 70, Day 84, and Day 98 in (a) R1; (b) R2; (c) R3; (d) R4. (B-An: Before anaerobic stage; An: at end of anaerobic stage; Ae: at end of aerobic stage; End: end of the cycle).

Fig. 4. Cyclic profiles of three key polymers observed in sediment/sludge: (a)-(d) poly-P in R1, R2, R3 and R4; (e)-(h) PHA in R1, R2, R3 and R4; (i)-(l) glycogen in R1, R2, R3 and R4, respectively.

3.3. Intracellular polymers responses

As we all know, traditional EBPR systems operate based on the anaerobic P release and aerobic P uptake by PAOs. During the anaerobic stage, organic matters uptake and PHA synthesis occurred simultaneously, accompanied by the P releasing from the cleavage of polyphosphate (poly-P) and the glycolysis of glycogen. In the aerobic stage, released P was utilized to synthesize poly-P utilizing stored PHA for energy [24,26]. As shown in Fig. 4, the trends of the three key polymers during the operation generally follow the expectations. The poly-P content in the sediment-inoculated reactors remained consistently low, with the highest value being only 9.4 mg P/g VSS in R1 after the aerobic stage on Day 70 (Fig. 4(a)). This value is considerably lower than reported by Long et al., who investigated cyclic changes of poly-P in the cells within SBRs. Their data indicated that the maximum content of poly-P at the end of aerobic phases in SBRs fed with acetate and propionate was approximately 60 mg P/g VSS and 25 mg P/g VSS, respectively [27]. In contrast, the propionate-fed sludge-inoculated SBR (R3) exhibited significantly higher values, reaching up to 58.0 mg P/g VSS (Fig. 4(c)). When the COD feeding concentration was increased to 400 mg/L, both sludge-seeded SBRs experienced severe poly-P loss. By Day 91, after the aerobic stage, the poly-P content in R3 had dropped to just 0.8 mg P/g VSS. When the COD concentration was adjusted back to 200 mg/L, there was a partial recovery in the poly-P in the sludge.

On Day 77, at the end of the anaerobic phase, the PHA contents of R1 and R3 were 230.2 and 172.5 mg C/g VSS, respectively, representing increases of 56.7 % and 17.0 % compared to the initial content of this cycle. The anaerobic synthesis rate of PHA was 41.5 mg C/g VSS \cdot h⁻¹ for sediment-inoculated and 12.5 mg C/g VSS \cdot h⁻¹ for sludge-inoculated SBR, both higher than previously reported rates of 10 mg C/g VSS \cdot h⁻¹ [27] and 2 mg C/g VSS \cdot h⁻¹ [4] in different EBPR systems. However, the following variation in PHA content indicates that increasing the C feeding concentration did not enhance PHA synthesis. On the contrary, during the 400 mg/L COD feeding phase, PHA content in all SBRs decreased and did not recover even when the COD concentration was adjusted back to 200 mg/L after Day 105. Aerobic hydrolysis of intracellular PHAs provided the necessary energy. Since the PHA/P ratio reflects the efficiency of PAOs in utilizing internally stored organic polymers for P uptake, its decline indicates a severe decrease in the SBRs' ability to accumulate organic P [28,29]. This decline might be due to changes in the microbial community within the SBRs, with GAOs potentially becoming more dominant and leading to the storage of glycogen rather than PHA under anaerobic conditions [30]. This observation aligns with the trends in glycogen shown in Fig. 4. Increasing the C feeding concentration to 400 mg/L raised glycogen levels in the propionic acid-fed reactors R1 and R3, particularly in R3. As shown in Fig. 4(k), glycogen content in the sludge of R3 significantly increased from 7.5 mg C/g VSS on Day 84 to 16.9 mg C/g VSS on Day 91 and 36.8 mg C/g VSS on Day 98 (all data refer to the end of the aerobic stage). Additionally, glycogen content at the end of the anaerobic phase was higher than at the end of the aerobic phase on Days 91 and 98.

Summarizing the variations in the three key polymers, we can conclude that when the EBPR system (R1 and R3) operated stably, the corresponding polymers also remain stable at corresponding levels. However, when the C feeding concentration is too high (COD = 400 mg/L) and the SBRs exhibited deterioration, the levels of poly-P and PHA decreased significantly, while glycogen synthesis increased. This could be due to changes in microbial activity driven by the altered C concentration, leading to different metabolic preferences. These observations suggest that, glycolysis of glycogen by PAOs under anaerobic conditions is not the primary reaction under 400 mg/L COD feeding. Instead, anaerobic glycogen synthesis from propionate may have become the dominant metabolic pathway, potentially due to competition between GAOs and PAOs. The underlying microbial mechanisms related to these changes will be explored and validated through detailed microbial activity analysis, which will be discussed in the next section.

3.4. Adaptation of microbial community

To understand the microbial community structure, the DNA samples were sequenced, resulting in 12661.919 \pm 3630.931 reads per sample and a total number of 8139 ASVs. Rarefaction was performed at the lowest number of reads (6341). The microbial α -diversity results are shown in Fig. S5. The analysis indicated a significant decrease in α -diversity for R2-R4 starting from Day 28 ($p < 0.05$), whereas for R1, the significant decrease began from Day 56. Metagenomic analysis revealed that varying concentrations and types of C sources lead to divergent evolutionary paths in the microbial communities of sediment and sludge. At the phylum level, data from the first DNA sample collection point after Day 0, which is Day 28, indicate significant differences in the microbial communities of all reactors compared to the initial state ($p < 0.001$). Despite the significant differences in the microbial structure of sediment and sludge ($p < 0.001$), both were dominated by the phyla Proteobacteria, Actinobacteriota, and Bacteroidota (Fig. 5). The primary functions of these phyla, which include nitrogen assimilation and organic matter degradation, are also observed in sewage sludge [31,32]. Initially, these phyla constituted 30.5 %, 9.2 %, and 8.8 % for sediment, and 35.8 %, 8.7 %, and 22.5 % for sludge, respectively. Interestingly, in the reactors fed with propionic acid, the relative abundance of Proteobacteria gradually increased, reaching a peak of 65.8 % in R1 and 60.8 % in R3. Conversely, in the glucose-fed reactors R2 and R4, the abundance of Actinobacteriota increased, with maximum abundances of 56.8 % and 50.2 %, respectively.

The abundance of *Rhodocyclaceae* was significantly higher in R1 compared to the initial relative abundance, increasing from almost 0 % to 16.0 % on Day 42. However, after Day 84 (during the 400 mg/L COD feeding phase), it dropped sharply to just 5.4 % by Day 119. *Rhodocyclaceae*, a member of the β -Proteobacteria, is known for its P removal capabilities. Some members of this family, such as those belonging to the genus *Candidatus Accumulibacter*, are well-known PAOs [33]. Additionally, previous studies have shown that some microorganisms within the *Rhodocyclaceae* family, but unrelated to *Candidatus Accumulibacter*, may act as potential PAOs for performing EBPR. The enrichment of *Rhodocyclaceae* can ensure stable and efficient P removal even when the *Accumulibacter* population decreases [33,34]. The activated sludge inoculated SBRs initially contained PAOs (6.4 % of *Rhodocyclaceae*) and a relatively low abundance of GAOs (0.1 % of *Competibacteraceae*). Although PAO abundance declined during the operation of the SBR, feeding 200 mg/L of propionic acid (R3) allowed the EBPR process to operate stably, demonstrating relatively satisfactory P release and uptake capabilities.

Sediment-seeded reactors fed with glucose (R2) also exhibited a rapid proliferation of *Rhodocyclaceae*, reaching a maximum relative abundance of 19.3 % on Day 56. However, in R2, the *Propionibacteriaceae* family grew even faster, increasing from approximately 0 % initially to 42.3 % on Day 115. Similarly, in the glucose-fed sludge seeded SBR (R4), *Propionibacteriaceae* showed rapid growth, from 1.1 % initially to 22.9 % on Day 91. *Propionibacteriaceae* possess strong acid-producing activity, transforming proteins, lactic acid, and carbohydrates into propionic acid and CO₂, thereby providing nutrients for microorganisms. Although Gui et al. [35] indicated that the removal efficiency of total nitrogen, total P, and COD was significantly positively correlated with *Propionibacteriaceae*. In our study, the considerable enrichment of *Propionibacteriaceae* did not contribute to P removal. This is evident from the similar influent and effluent concentrations of PO₄-P in R2 and R4 observed throughout the experiment.

According to previous studies, introducing glucose in the influent could lead to the breakdown of the EBPR process [36]. For example, Cech et al. [37,38] attributed the poor EBPR performance to the presence of glucose in the influent, which resulted in GAOs dominating, and GAOs cannot accumulate poly-P. The family *Competibacteraceae* is known to include GAOs (e.g., *Candidatus Competibacter*). However, the enrichment of GAOs within *Competibacteraceae* in R2 was not significant,

Fig. 5. Compositional structure of microbial communities at phylum level during different period in (a) R1, (b) R2, R3 and (d) R4.

with the highest detected relative abundance being 5.9 % on Day 84 (Fig. 6(b)). Jeon et al. [39], after more than 250 days of SBR operation, proposed and verified a model suggesting a potential metabolic pathway for PHA synthesis and P removal in SBRs using glucose as the sole C source. They suggested that in SBRs with glucose as the sole C source, lactic acid-producing organisms (LPOs) accumulate glucose as glycogen and subsequently convert it to lactic acid polymers. Then, PAOs anaerobically absorb and convert the lactic acid into PHA, meanwhile consuming poly-P and releasing phosphate, thereby achieving stable EBPR operation. Based on the above theory, although PAOs were enriched in R2, the abundance of LPOs was too low (with relative abundance at the family level < 1 %). This indicates that the original LPO abundance in our system was considerably low; and feeding glucose as the sole C source, followed by anaerobic/aerobic cycling, did not promote LPO enrichment. Not only did the sediment-seeded reactor (R2) face this issue, but the sludge-seeded reactor (R4) encountered the same limitation. As a result, the process where LPOs would normally uptake glucose and convert it into lactic acid polymers did not occur. Therefore, there were no lactate polymers available for PAOs to use for PHA synthesis and phosphate release. Conversely, as we previously mentioned, the reactors fed with glucose showed a rapid proliferation of *Propionibacteriaceae* during operation. This enrichment most likely competed with LPOs for C uptake, further inhibiting the metabolic pathways responsible for P release. Consequently, although an increase in PAO abundance was observed in both R2 and R4, neither reactor exhibited EBPR performance at any stage of operation. Thus, in our experiment, EBPR process was unsuccessful when glucose was used as the sole C source.

To further understand the responses from specific PAOs and GAOs, typical and putative PAOs/GAOs with a relative abundance greater than

1 % at the genus level have been selected and presented in Fig. S6. *Candidatus Accumulibacter* is now widely recognized as a main PAO, performing the function of biological P removal [33,40]. On the other hand, *Dechloromonas*, belonging to the family *Rhodocyclaceae*, has been identified as a putative PAO with different P removal metabolic characteristics. *Dechloromonas* can achieve simultaneous nitrogen and P removal in anoxic conditions through a denitrifying P removal pathway [40], while *Thauera* plays a similar role [41]. All of these genera were detected at relatively high abundances in our SBRs. Other species of putative PAOs, such as those from the genus *Tetrasphaera*, were detected at very low abundances [40]. Likewise, GAOs such as *Candidatus Competibacter* and putative GAO genera like *Deftuviococcus* and *Nakamurella* were also selected [42].

The abundance of putative PAOs/GAOs was almost 0 % in the sediment-inoculated SBRs on Day 0; while the initial corresponding values in the sludge-seeded SBRs was also relatively low (<1%). However, with the alternation of anaerobic and aerobic conditions in the SBR reactors, the abundance of these species increased. When the COD feeding concentration gradually increased to 400 mg/L, R1 and R3 began to exhibit EBPR breakdown. An interesting result was observed: in R1, there was no significant decrease in PAOs, but GAOs increased substantially. Conversely, in R3, PAOs decreased, but GAOs did not increase significantly. Despite the different microbial responses within sediment and sludge inoculated SBRs, both results indicated that the excessive increase in feeding C concentration leads to GAO competition over PAO, ultimately resulting in the deterioration of EBPR. This observation supports our previous hypothesis that the decline in EBPR performance at high C concentrations is due to competitive GAOs, as discussed in the key polymers section.

To further investigate the correlation between environmental

Fig. 6. Compositional structure of microbial communities at family level during different period in (a) R1, (b) R2, R3 and (d) R4.

Fig. 7. Pearson correlation analysis between different indicators and typical and putative PAO/GAO in the SBR of (a) R1, (b) R2, R3 and (d) R4 (An: at the end of anaerobic stage; Ae: at the end of aerobic stage).

parameters and genera abundance, a correlation analysis was carried out (Fig. 7). The results showed that in R1, high concentration of C promoted the enrichment of GAOs ($p < 0.01$) but significantly inhibited the aerobic synthesis of glycogen ($p < 0.05$), leading to a decline in EBPR performance. In R3, the analysis indicated that the rate of anaerobic P release and anaerobic PHA synthesis in the sludge was significantly positively correlated with the presence of putative PAOs (Dechloromonas) but negatively correlated with GAOs ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, putative PAOs (*Defluviococcus*) were found to enhance aerobic glycogen synthesis.

Building on the discussion above, we can propose and summarize the potential mechanisms involved during reactor operation. The alternation between anaerobic and aerobic conditions favors the enrichment of both PAOs and GAOs. Although the relative abundance of GAOs/putative GAOs appears to exceed that of PAOs, R1 and R3, which were fed with propionic acid, still exhibited good EBPR performance with influent COD levels of 100–200 mg/L. However, when the COD concentration increased to 400 mg/L, a decline in PAO abundance in R1 and an increase in GAO abundance in R3 led to competition from GAOs over PAOs, resulting in the breakdown of EBPR performance. This was specifically reflected in the decreased levels of poly-P and PHA, along with a significant increase in glycogen synthesis. In the glucose-fed sediment/sludge systems (R2 and R4), the lack of LPO and the inability to enrich PAOs through anaerobic-aerobic alternation hindered the pathway for lactate synthesis from glucose, which explains the absence of EBPR performance throughout the operation. Despite a certain abundance of PAOs being detected in R2 and R4, above limitation may be a key factor preventing successful EBPR operation. In contrast, the propionic acid-fed systems, under 200 mg/L COD, facilitated more efficient PAO enrichment due to a direct metabolic pathway for poly-P glycolysis and phosphate release. The relevant mechanisms are illustrated in Fig. 8.

3.5. Stimulation of phosphorus precipitation

As outlined in Section 3.1, the maximum P concentration in the supernatant from our experiment (70–80 mg/L) offers a valuable basis for future precipitation-based P recovery trials. For the simulation work, we used the solution collected after the anaerobic phase of the R1 reactor during Day 70–80 as an example. Using the PHREEQC software, we simulated the precipitation of P as struvite ($\text{NH}_4\text{MgPO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) under different pH conditions. The relevant code can be found in the

supplementary material. The calculated saturation index (SI) and theoretical P yield are shown in Fig. S7. As illustrated, when the solution's pH increased from 7.5 to 9.2, the SI rose from 0.22 to 1.34. Since $\text{SI} > 0$ indicates supersaturation, the mineral should precipitate [43]. The theoretical P yield also increased from 7.7 % to 94.8 %, indicating that the P-rich solution obtained at the end of the anaerobic phase holds significant potential as a promising source for P recovery.

3.6. Implications of the study

In this experiment, we focus a previously unexplored area of research by investigating the feasibility of enriching PAOs in marine sediment using alternating anaerobic and aerobic conditions. The results demonstrated that feeding an appropriate concentration of propionic acid can realize the goal. Although glucose feeding can also enrich PAOs in sediment, operating successful EBPR with glucose requires different microbial metabolic pathways. The lack of enrichment of LPOs in sediment prevents the metabolic pathway for anaerobic P release and aerobic removal. Although the microbial structure of marine sediment differs from that of sludge, some commonalities were observed during the operation of the SBRs. Therefore, knowledge from the wastewater treatment field can provide valuable guidance for P recovery from marine systems.

Our previous batch experiments indicated that sediment, especially collected from eutrophic areas, contains a certain amount of P, but most of it exists in an inactive fraction. This makes P very difficult to be released by simply adding C sources under anaerobic conditions. In our earlier batch study, after 15 days of anaerobic operation, less than 4 % of total P could be released, and the consumption of VFAs was negligible. We speculated that this could be due to the low presence of bacteria in the original sediment capable of anaerobically consuming C sources and releasing P, such as PAOs. Therefore, our experiment provides a technical route and theoretical basis for enriching PAOs within sediments. Additionally, the PHREEQC simulation results demonstrated the potential for P recovery from anaerobic P-rich supernatant through precipitation techniques. Future experiments could focus on enhancing the anaerobic release of P, particularly organic P, by seeding fresh sediment with PAO-rich material. This approach could help achieve a higher proportion of P release and recovery from sediments. It is worth noting that further experimental optimization of precipitation parameters is needed to refine this recovery process.

Fig. 8. Potential mechanism of PAO in propionic acid-fed vs. glucose-fed SBRs.

4. Conclusion

Our study has investigated the feasibility of enriching PAOs from sediment using alternating anaerobic and aerobic conditions to achieve EBPR, with future applications in P recovery. The experimental results showed that sediment inoculated SBR fed with propionic acid exhibited excellent P release/uptake performance after 56 days of cultivation, with maximum P release and uptake rates of 3 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹ and 2.5 mg P/g VSS•h⁻¹, respectively. After 42 days of operation, the abundance of PAO family (*Rhodocyclaceae*) in the sediment fed with propionic acid (200 mg/L COD) increased from almost 0 to 16.0 %. As a reference, sludge inoculated SBR fed with propionic acid also demonstrated good EBPR performance. However, in glucose-fed SBRs, although PAOs were enriched, the lack of LPOs prevented the system from converting glucose into lactic acid for PAOs to utilize, thereby hindering successful EBPR operation. When the COD feeding concentration increased to 400 mg/L, both R1 and R3 showed significant EBPR deterioration, specifically indicated by the loss of anaerobic P release and aerobic P uptake capabilities, as well as a continuous decrease in total P content in the SBRs. From the microbial responses perspective, this could be attributed to GAO competition over PAOs.

Our study also highlights the importance of assessing C consumption capacity during the anaerobic phase in the acclimation stage. This capacity can be used to determine whether the C feeding concentration should be increased in subsequent operational stages. By collecting P-rich solution from the anaerobic phase of R1, we conducted software simulations and found that adjusting the pH to 9.2 could theoretically recover P as struvite, with a recovery yield of up to 94 %.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fengyi Zhu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elena Radaelli:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sri Laxma Alankar Senthilnathan:** Investigation. **Giorgia Palladino:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Federica D'Amico:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Frederico Marques Penha:** Software. **Silvia Turroni:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Zeynep Cetecioglu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.157888>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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